

PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN MEDIA TEXTS AS AN OBJECT OF RESEARCH

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АННОТАЦИЯ

*Статья посвящена исследованию особенностей фразеологических единиц (ФЕ) в медиатексте. Рассматривается роль фразеологизмов в формировании образов политиков в англоязычной прессе (на примере образов В. Путина). Отмечается, что благодаря метафоричности, экспрессивности и эмоциональности ФЕ использование фразеологизмов является одним из эффективных средств создания образа, где особую важность имеет эмоционально-оценочная составляющая. Источником материала послужили тексты англоязычных газетных и журнальных статей из качественных британских и американских изданий, в частности, *The Economist*, *The Guardian*, *The Newsweek*, *The Telegraph*, *The Washington Post*, *Forbes*, а также электронных ресурсов: *Defense one*, *Project Syndicate* за период с 2009 по 2016 год.*

Ключевые слова: медиатекст, медиадискурс, образ политика, фразеологизм, языковые средства, пресса

ANNOTATION

The article is devoted to the study of the features of phraseological units (PU) in media discourse. The role of phraseological units in the formation of images of politicians in the English-language press is considered (using the images of V. Putin as an example). It is noted that due to the metaphorical, expressiveness and emotionality of phraseological units, the use of phraseological units is one of the effective means of creating an image, where the emotional and evaluative component

is of particular importance. The source of the material was the texts of English-language newspaper and magazine articles from high-quality British and American publications, in particular, The Economist, The Guardian, The Newsweek, The Telegraph, The Washington Post, Forbes, as well as electronic resources: Defense one, Project Syndicate for the period from 2009 to 2016

Keywords: *media text, media discourse, image of a politician, phraseological unit, linguistic means, press*

In the paradigm of modern linguistics, interest in various types of discourse prevails. In particular, the media discourse, or media discourse, which, due to globalization processes, has become an integral part of the social life of a modern person, is increasingly in the focus of researchers' attention: "mass media texts, or media texts, are one of the most common forms of the modern existence of a language, and their total length far exceeds the total volume of speech in other spheres of human activity" [1, p. 5]. Modern media unite the information space of states and peoples, form an understanding of reality in its political, social and other aspects among the audience all over the world.

The studies available in the field of phraseology show that the word "phraseology" has several meanings. As a linguistic term, it is used to refer to a special branch of linguistics that studies "stable phrases with complicated semantics that are not formed according to generating structural-semantic models of variable combinations" [7. P. 5], called phraseological units, or phraseological units (less often phraseological turns), as well as to designate a set of similar phrases characteristic of a given language. Referring to the etymology of the term, phraseology is defined as "the science of the phrase", although most often it does not denote the science itself, but rather its material. Phraseology studies include only phraseological units, which are referred to differently in different sources: "indecomposable combinations" (Chess), "stable combinations" (Abakumov) or "unchanging expressions" (set expressions) (Arnold), that is, close unities consisting from several words and expressing a holistic concept.

Phraseology is evidence of brightness, colorfulness language. Phraseological units reflect the history of the people, the originality of their culture and way of life. The images embedded in phraseological units serve as a reflection of the national identity of the people, and therefore phraseological units often have a clearly national character. Along with completely national phraseological units, there are many international phraseological units in the phraseology of different languages. In some phraseological units, archaic elements are preserved - representatives of previous eras.

PhUs fill the gaps in the lexical system of the language, which cannot fully provide the name of the (new) sides of reality known to man, and in many cases are the only designations for objects, properties, processes, states, situations, etc.

One of the basic directions for the formation of socio-political reality through media discourse is the creation of images of political figures. In this study, following E.S. Aznaurova, E.S. Kubryakova, I.V. Arnold, N.D. Harutyun's image is understood as a category of consciousness, it combines the data coming through different channels of communication between a person and the world. "The process of image formation is complex and multifaceted. First of all, the author of a publication, that is, a journalist of one or another publication, creates an image based on certain standardized ideas, adapting to social reality. On the other hand, he

influences the reproduction of these ideas, broadcasting them through linguistic means to the reader and fixing them in the mass consciousness" [2, p. 26].

It is worth emphasizing that the emotional-evaluative component is of particular importance in the images. That is why journalists often use phraseological resources that have such qualities as metaphor, expressiveness, and emotionality.

In this paper, we consider the concept of phraseological units in a broad sense, based on the definition of phraseological units proposed by N.M. Shansky, where phraseological turnover is "a linguistic unit reproduced in finished form, consisting of two or more stressed components of a verbal character, fixed (i.e. constant) in its meaning, composition and structure" [3, p. 44]. In accordance with this approach, the main types of phraseological units are considered not only phraseological units,

phraseological units, phraseological combinations, but also phraseological expressions (idiomatic phrases, proverbs, proverbs, aphorisms).

It should be noted that the texts of the articles analyzed by us are dominated not by political phraseological units proper denoting political phenomena (cold war), but by phraseological units that fit into the fabric of a journalistic text, but are not directly related to political topics and are used only to characterize it. So, for example, in articles where the personality of V. Putin appears, quite a lot of phraseological units related to gambling are used:

- Putin has quickly upped the ante (‘поднять ставки’), forcing Washington to refocus on facts on the ground [Defense One, 29.09.2015].

- An all-in Putin (от ФЕ to be all in ‘ready to risk everything, put everything on the line’) would step beyond Obama’s red line in the ISIS fight [Defense One, 29.09.2015]. This characterizes the Russian president not only as an adventurer, a person ready to take risks, but also as a player who skillfully misleads others and bluffs:

- Poker-face Putin holds all the cards (‘have an advantage’) [The Telegraph, 14.09.2013].

- Putin Threatens World War Again, This Time Over Syria: Will Turks And Saudis Call His Bluff? [Forbes 16.02.2016] (‘bring it to clean water’, lit. “accused of bluffing”).

- Journalists of English-language publications emphasize the unpredictability and some impunity of V. Putin’s actions: Market reaction suggests sanctions over Crimea are slap on the wrist for Putin [The Guardian, 17.04. 2014].

- Putin’s statement hit like a bolt from the blue (‘Like a bolt from the blue’) [Project syndicate, 29.06.2009].

Thus, the media discourse, which is the focus of this study, is a battlefield of various ideological attitudes and pragmatic interests, and phraseological units are strong emotionally influencing means of influencing the speech addressee, with the help of which journalists create vivid images of political leaders, while forming a certain attitude of readers to a particular person.

LITERATURE

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